

APPENDIX

A. Locality level of Missing contexts in Single-shard Settings

Another important question is why some cases fail in the Single-shard setting but succeed in the Cross-shard setting. Specifically, we want to understand what factors contribute to this difference. We define the locality level as the percentage of contexts found within the same file as the completion point, but in a different revision. For Python, among the 26 datapoints missed by the Single-shard setting, Cross-shard queries were able to find 57.1% of them in the same file as the completion point. For Kotlin, this percentage is even higher: 68.1% out of 46 missed datapoints. This shows that a significant portion of useful contexts can be found in the same file, but across other timeframes, rather than just the current one where the completion point is resided. Figure 5 shows the distribution of locality levels for both Python and Kotlin.

Locality Level of Contexts found in Cross-shard setting (Python)

Locality Level of Contexts found in Cross-shard setting (Kotlin)

Fig. 5: Locality level of missing contexts in Single-shard Settings for Python (top) and Kotlin (bottom).

Languages	Diff string
Python	<pre> import csv, codecs, cStringIO class UTF8Recoder: """ Iterator that reads an encoded stream and reencodes the input to UTF-8 """ def __init__(self, f, encoding): self.reader = codecs.getreader(encoding)(f) /**<FIM>*/ class UnicodeReader: """ A CSV reader which will iterate over lines in the CSV file "f" which is encoded in the given encoding. """ def __init__(self, f, dialect=csv.excel, encoding="utf-8", ** kwds): f = UTF8Recoder(f, encoding) self.reader = csv.reader(f, dialect=dialect, **kwds) def next(self): row = self.reader.next() return [unicode(s, "utf-8") for s in row] def __iter__(self): return self </pre>
Kotlin	<pre> DropdownMenu(expanded = expanded, onDismissRequest = {expanded = false},) { DropdownMenuItem(text = { Text(stringResource(R.string. dropdownmenu_settings)) }, onClick = { navController.navigate(SettingsNavScreens.Settings.route) { p } }) } </pre>

TABLE V: Diff examples corresponding to Revision 6cbd23 (Python) and Revision 797c52 (Kotlin)

Query Variation	Code Snippet
functions_classes_naive	<code>navigate Text stringResource DropdownMenuItem DropdownMenu</code>
functions_classes_or	<code>navigate or Text or stringResource or DropdownMenuItem or DropdownMenu</code>
functions_classes_top5	<code>navigate Text stringResource DropdownMenuItem DropdownMenu</code>
functions_classes_top4	<code>navigate Text stringResource DropdownMenuItem</code>
functions_classes_top3	<code>navigate Text stringResource</code>
functions_classes_regex	<code>DropdownMenu.*navigate</code>
navigation_naive	<code>navController.navigate SettingsNavScreens.Settings.route SettingsNavScreens.Settings R.string.dropdownmenu.settings R.string</code>
navigation_unpacked	<code>R NavController string SettingsNavScreens Settings route</code>
navigation_unpacked_or	<code>R or NavController or string or SettingsNavScreens or Settings or route</code>
navigation_unpacked_top5	<code>R NavController string SettingsNavScreens Settings</code>
navigation_unpacked_top4	<code>R NavController string SettingsNavScreens</code>
navigation_unpacked_top3	<code>R NavController string</code>
navigation_regex	<code>R.*route</code>
identifiers_naive	<code>Text Settings dropdownmenu_settings R NavController text</code>
identifiers_or	<code>Text or Settings or dropdownmenu_settings or R or NavController or text</code>
identifiers_top5	<code>Text Settings dropdownmenu_settings R NavController</code>
identifiers_top4	<code>Text Settings dropdownmenu_settings R</code>
identifiers_top3	<code>Text Settings dropdownmenu_settings</code>
identifiers_regex	<code>DropdownMenu.*p</code>

TABLE VI: Table of generated query variation for Revision 797c52 (Kotlin) .

Languages	Function and Class, Navigation Expression, and Wild Identifiers
Scheme	<pre>;; Function and Class extraction (Tree-sitter query) (class_definition name: (identifier) @class.name) (function_definition name: (identifier) @function.name) (call function: [(identifier) @function.name (attribute (identifier) @function.name)]) (parameters (identifier) @parameter.name) (argument_list (identifier) @argument.name)</pre>
	<pre>;; Navigation Expression extraction (Tree-sitter query) (call function: (attribute (identifier)) @navigation_expression)</pre>
	<pre>;; Wild Identifiers extraction (Tree-sitter query) (identifier) @identifier</pre>
Scheme	<pre>;;; Class definitions ;; Regular classes, data classes, sealed classes, abstract classes (class_declaration (type_identifier) @class.name) ;; Object declarations (singletons) (object_declaration (type_identifier) @object.name) ;; Companion objects (class_body (companion_object (type_identifier)? @companion.name) ; name is optional)</pre>
	<pre>;; Navigation Expression (navigation_expression) @navigation_expression</pre>
	<pre>;; Wild Identifiers extraction (simple_identifier) @identifier (type_identifier) @type_identifier</pre>

TABLE VII: Tree sitter schemes to gather symbols.

L = Maximum number of tokens that Mellum can handle

Pr = Number of tokens in the prefix of diff string

Suf = Number of tokens in the suffix of diff string

$Reserve$ = Small buffer to ensure generation space

T = Context budget = $L - Pr - Suf - Reserve$

K = top k files

$$M = \left\lfloor \frac{T}{K} \right\rfloor$$

(1)

$R = T$

For each file/snippet:

 If tokens $\leq M$ and $R - \text{tokens} \geq 0$:

$R = R - \text{tokens}$

 Add context

Stop when $R \leq 0$